

Short Research Study

Evaluation of Sealing Ability of Three Different Root Canal Sealers

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Abstract

Aim: To evaluate the sealing ability of three different root canal sealers.

Material and Methods: The 30 extracted single rooted teeth were taken and stored in 1% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) solution, for three days to remove organic debris and then they were stored in distilled water. The crowns were removed at the cement-enamel junction using a high-speed fissure bur. Access preparation was done using an endo access bur followed by biomechanical preparation of the root canal. After drying the canals with paper points, standardized gutta-percha cones were selected as master points. The fit of each master point was assessed by radiographs to determine whether the point was fully seated to the working length. The teeth were randomly selected and divided into three groups of 10 teeth each. The sealers used were as follow Group 1: AH plus (DENTSPLY) (Resin Based), Group 2: Eposeal, Group 3: Bioceramic (SAFE ENDO). The master gutta-percha point was coated with sealer and placed in the canal to the full working length and obturation was done. The post obturation restoration was done with composite. The samples were sectioned longitudinally by means of a low-speed circular diamond saw in a path roughly parallel to the axis of the tooth and through the apex. After sectioning, the samples were studied under higher magnification.

Results: AH plus has better sealing ability followed by bioceramic followed by eposeal.

Conclusion: AH plus has better sealing ability and it can be used as sealer during root canal treatment.

Key words: AH plus, Eposeal, Bioceramic, Higher magnification, Gutta Percha.

Introduction:

A "perfect" or hermetic apical seal, the removal of any entry or exit portal to the periapical tissues, & the obturation of the root canal area with an inert filler material are all necessary for successful endodontic treatment. In addition, it ought to be dimensionally stable, nontoxic and biocompatible with the tissue fluids. The main goals of root canal obturation were to stop bacteria from growing inside the canal, ensnaring any leftover bacteria, and completely obturating the channel at the microscopic level to prevent stagnant fluid from building up and providing nourishment for micro organisms from all sources. Gutta-percha is the most widely used ortho grade obturating technique in the

world. Because gutta-percha's weak sealing qualities prevent it from completely obturating the root canal system, a sealer is employed in addition to gutta percha. The sealer is used in all modern obturating procedures to improve the root canal filling's seal.¹ A semisolid, solid, or rigid core material is cemented in the canal using a root canal sealer as a binding agent in the most widely used method of canal obturation. Sealer achieves the goal of creating a fluid tight seal. The core

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takes up space and acts as a sealer delivery system.² The sealer can be made to flow & fill the many apical foramina as well as the auxiliary canal before it sets. Numerous root canal sealants are there and are categorized depending on their chemical makeup: resin-based, eugenol based, or calcium hydroxide-based. This study was done to evaluate effectiveness of sealing property of different root canal sealers.

Materials & Methods

A total of 30 single rooted extracted human teeth with a single root canal were selected. Teeth with single-rooted extracted permanent teeth with a single root canal were included. Teeth with the curvature greater than 5 degrees, with the evident root fracture, incompletely formed apex, bifurcating canals, fins, ribbon-shaped canal or extreme calcifications were excluded in this study.

The teeth were stored in 1% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) solution, for three days to remove organic debris and then they were stored in distilled water. The crowns were removed at the cement-enamel junction using a high-speed fissure bur. Access preparation was done using an endo access bur. Then, a no.10 – K-file was introduced into the canal and was pushed towards apical part until the tip of the instrument was just visible at the apical foramen. This length of the file was recorded and then after subtracting 1mm from the recorded length, working length of the root canal was determined. The canals were cleaned and shaped with K-files using a step-back technique with recapitulation of files to establish a progressively tapering root canal preparation. The apical portion of the canal was enlarged to a minimum 30 no. K-file and 50 no. K-file, depending on the size of the original canal. After each instrument was used, the canals were irrigated with 2ml of 5% NaOCl and normal saline. After drying the canals with paper points, standardized gutta-percha cones were selected as master points. The fit of each master point was assessed by radiographs to determine whether the point was fully seated to the working length. The teeth were randomly selected and divided into three groups of 10 teeth each. The sealers used were as follows

- Group 1: AH plus (DENTSPLY) (Resin Based)
- Group 2: Eposeal
- Group 3: Bioceramic (SAFE ENDO)

The sealers were mixed according to the manufacturer's directions. The master gutta-percha point was coated with sealer and placed in the canal to the full working length. Hand spreader was then used for lateral condensation with standardized fine gutta-percha accessory points was carried out until the entire canal

was obturated. Radiographs were taken to evaluate the obturation. Obturation was considered to be optimum when no voids were present in the radiograph. The post obturation restoration was done with composite.

The samples were sectioned longitudinally by means of a low speed circular diamond saw in a path roughly parallel to the axis of the tooth and through the apex. After sectioning, the samples were studied under higher magnification.

Discussion:

The majority of the time, rigid, semisolid, or solid core materials are used to obturate root canals. Gutta-percha is the most often utilized core material, yet when used by itself, it does not seal the canal. So, root canal sealers are used with gutta-percha. To achieve long-term clinical success, the root canal space should be thoroughly cleaned and shaped before the complete root canal system is filled in three dimensions. The idea of an ideal apical seal has prompted researchers to look for filling and sealing materials that will offer an impeccable seal at the apical foramen while also being stable and non-irritating.^{3,4}

The concept of a perfect apical seal has led to search for filling and sealing materials that are stable, non-irritating and provide a flawless seal at the apical foramen. The selection of sealers is dependent on its capacity to create a comprehensive seal but it must also be well accepted by peri-radicular tissues and be comparatively easy to manipulate so that its optimum physical and biological properties can be clinically achieved. In principle the core material should push the less viscous into unreachable areas such as canal anastomosis, apical delta and into irregularities produced through canal preparation. The sealing ability of various root canal filling materials and root canal sealers have been studied and it has been found that dissimilar constituents seal the canal to different extents. Principle aim of canal cleaning and shaping is to eliminate all pulp material remnants and bacteria along with their substrates and optimum shaping of the root canal space.^{5,6}

Gold standard method of root canal obturation being a combination of gutta-percha cones and a sealer has been used in the present study.⁷ The teeth obturated with gutta-percha points and sealer display less leakage than those without sealer. Although several studies have shown good clinical results for many years, some in vitro and in vivo studies have demonstrated that they fail to achieve a complete root canal seal. The microleakage has been attributed to the lack of an effective bond at the sealer/dentin and sealer/gutta-percha interfaces. In this study, AH plus has better sealing ability followed by

bioceramic followed by eposeal.

Saeed, Shafer and Brackett et al. observed that resin-based root canal sealers were more effective in sealing root canals than the poly dimethylsiloxane based sealer.

Haddad AA et al evaluated and compared the sealer thickness and interfacial adaptation of bioceramic sealers to root dentin against AH Plus sealer. Bioceramic sealers showed more gaps compared with AH-Plus, with no significant differences among them.

Thakur P et al observed that AH plus have good sealing ability compared to apexit and zinc oxide based sealers.⁶ The leakage values obtained with AH Plus group were lesser than conventional zinc-oxide eugenol and Apexit. The reason could be attributed to the slight expansion that might occur tending to wedge the sealer more tightly into the prepared root canal, thereby improving the mechanical interlocking.^{8,9}

Rashid et al. evaluated the sealing ability of three commercially available endodontic sealers: Bioroot RCS (tricalcium silicate-based), Nanoseal S (polydimethyl siloxane based), and eposeal (epoxy-based resin). They found that eposeal exhibited the least dye penetration, followed by Bioroot RC, and Nanoseal S showed the highest dye penetration.¹⁰

Thakur et al. compared the apical sealing ability of four endodontic sealers: conventional zinc oxide eugenol sealer, Apexit, AH-Plus, and Roekoseal Automix (RSA). RSA, a polydimethyl siloxane based sealer, demonstrated significantly better apical sealing compared to the other sealers.

Pallavi et al. investigated the microleakage of two endodontic sealers, AH Plus and MTA Fillapex, placed using two different techniques: master gutta-percha cone and size 30 lentulospiral. MTA Fillapex placed using lentulospiral achieved the highest apical seal among all the groups.

However, till date, no sealer has been shown to be totally satisfactory for clinical use. The materials that have been used for obturation of root canal system, they have their own advantages and disadvantages and there is no single material or technique available so far, that fulfill all the requirement of root canal obturation.

Conclusion:

Within the limitation of the study, it was concluded that AH plus has better sealing ability followed by bioceramic followed by eposeal.

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